

Comparative Modelling of Cycling Route Choice by Bikes and E-Bikes: The Case Study of Tartu, Estonia

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Abstract. Cycling plays a crucial role in sustainable urban mobility, prompting cities worldwide to increase its modal share. A fundamental step in promoting cycling is understanding cyclists' route choice behaviour, which informs the design of a more efficient and attractive cycling infrastructure. In this study, we use high-resolution, long-term GPS data to model the route choice behaviour of cyclists. Furthermore, we focus on the differences in route choice between e-bike and conventional bicycle users. To our knowledge, it is the first to analyse cycling route choice in Estonia and the broader Central and Eastern European (CEE) region, utilising one of the most comprehensive datasets available on urban cycling. Our findings provide valuable insights to support evidence-based urban planning and cycling policy development, contributing to more cyclist-friendly cities.

Keywords. E-bikes, GPS, route choice modelling

1. Introduction

Understanding the travel behaviour and route preferences of cyclists in urban areas is essential for designing cost-effective policies and infrastructure interventions which promote cycling. The rising popularity of e-bikes has significantly altered urban cycling dynamics by enabling longer trips with less physical effort. However, transport models often treat bicycle traffic as a uniform mode of travel, despite growing evidence that e-bike and conventional bicycle users exhibit distinct behavioural patterns. Furthermore, it is particularly important to differentiate between the different e-bike user groups for

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targeted policy and infrastructure planning (Arning et al., 2023). The dataset used in our study from the city of Tartu, Estonia, is unique as it includes trip data from both conventional and e-bike users, enabling a comparative analysis of the factors influencing cycling route choice preferences.

Only three studies have directly compared the route choice behaviour of e-bike and conventional bicycle users. Dane et al. (2020) examined the influence of individual and contextual factors on trip distance but did not derive policy-relevant insights related to infrastructure or the built environment. Meister et al. (2023) developed a model for Zurich, Switzerland, revealing that e-bike users exhibit lower preferences for roads with a 30 km/h speed limit compared to conventional cyclists. Khavarian et al. (2024) found, among other things, that e-bikes would remove the sensitivity of elderly people and female cyclists to heavy vehicular traffic alongside their cycling path. A recent review (Łukawska, 2024) classified factors affecting route choice into three categories: network factors describing the built environment, contextual factors describing the external circumstances in the moment of choice, and individual factors of the person making the decision. Łukawska (2024) found that perceived safety, such as separation from motorised traffic, has the most important effect on route choice. Our study adds to the existing research by using an extensive revealed-preference dataset on cycling trips, including socio-demographic attributes (age and gender), to analyse the differences in route choice preferences between conventional and e-bike users based on network, contextual, and individual factors.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Case study area

Tartu is the second-largest city in Estonia with a population of 95 000 inhabitants. Since its launch in 2019, Tartu's bike-sharing system has demonstrated remarkable success, averaging around six trips per bike per day in its first year—placing it among the top ten most utilized bike-sharing systems worldwide (Saidla et al., 2024). The system operates on a dock-based model with 750 bicycles and 100 stations strategically distributed across the city. Notably, two-thirds of the fleet consists of e-bikes, enhancing accessibility and ease of use. However, only the 250 conventional bicycles remain in operation throughout the year, as e-bikes are subject to seasonal service limitations (Saidla et al., 2024).

2.2. Data

The spatial data for both network and contextual factors is sourced from OpenStreetMap (OSM). This includes data on the street network and cycling infrastructure, land use, and urban greenery, among many other factors. The network dataset for cycling within the study area spans a total length of 447 km. Cycling data is provided by the City of Tartu and covers all trips made by users of the bike-share system with a total of 581 583 trips. All bicycles are equipped with GPS sensors, which enable analysing the exact route taken by users. Furthermore, socio-demographic data, including age and gender, are included in the dataset. Additionally, several secondary datasets are incorporated to analyse the impact of built environment features on cycling route choice. While the list of variables is not exhaustive, key factors include gradient, provision of segregated cycling infrastructure, and other relevant characteristics. All secondary data sources are publicly available and sourced from OSM, the Estonian Land Board, and the City of Tartu.

2.3. Map-matching

Map-matching cycling trips to the street network based on GPS data poses several challenges and is more complex than for car trips (Berjisian & Bigazzi, 2023). In the bicycle route choice literature, there is no rigorous consensus about the best map-matching algorithm to apply for bicycle traffic. In this study, we employ an algorithm based on a hidden Markov model.

2.4. Route choice modelling

Analysing the factors influencing the route choice preferences of cyclists requires modelling possible non-chosen alternative routes between the cyclist's origin and destination. This is typically based on random utility theory, which assumes that individuals attempt to maximise the derived utility based on their preferences when choosing amongst alternatives (Dane et al., 2020). In this study, we use the path-size logit model presented by Ben-Akiva & Bierlaire (1999) to determine user preferences, which is commonly used in modelling cycling route choice (Łukawska, 2024). The model includes a path-size attribute indicating the proportion of the route constituting an independent alternative, thereby accounting for correlations among alternative routes, enabling the relatively simple Multinomial Logit (MNL) model structure to be used in discrete choice modelling.

3. Preliminary Results

In the current stage of our research, we are focusing on accurately map-matching the cycling trips to the street network. This will be followed by

estimating a model of cyclist's preferences using the discrete choice modeling framework. The preliminary results presented in this abstract showcase the richness of the GPS cycling data (figure 2) and some descriptive statistics of a small subset (2735 trips) from the dataset.

Figure 1 shows the map-matched routes of the subset, the busiest links in the network, and the locations of bike-share stations in Tartu. For each trip in the subset, we calculated the shortest route alternative between the origin and destination. The results show that on average, cyclists in Tartu deviate from the shortest route by 13%, which is similar to findings from earlier studies (Broach et al., 2012).

Figure 1. Map-matched bike-share trips in Tartu, Estonia. Only trips within the administrative borders are mapped.

3.1. Summary and planned results

Our study investigates behavioural differences in route selection between conventional and e-bike users by examining network characteristics, contextual factors, and individual attributes. Using a discrete choice framework, we

will develop a comprehensive route-choice model that quantifies how these factors differentially influence path selection decisions for each user group. What distinguishes our research is access to an exceptionally detailed urban cycling dataset, enabling a more thorough and detailed analysis than previous studies. The findings will identify specific variables that cyclists either prefer or avoid, revealing distinct preference patterns between conventional and e-bike users. These insights will directly inform evidence-based cycling infrastructure development and policy decisions, supporting more effective planning for diverse cycling populations.

Figure 2. Example of bike-share trip GPS points clearly showing the paths taken by cyclists.

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